

APPLICATION OF PERMANENT FORMWORK AS A RATIONAL APPROACH IN CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation: It would seem that everything in construction technology has long been invented and tested. But this is a mistaken opinion. With the advent of new materials, new, more progressive technologies are born, which very quickly spread and are implemented thanks to modern means of communication. The technology of building buildings using permanent formwork was no exception. Despite the fact that this technology appeared on construction sites relatively recently, it is becoming increasingly popular.

Key words: construction, foundation, new technology, blocks, panels, permanent formwork.

Introduction. The new construction method makes it possible to minimize the construction time of buildings and achieve a significant reduction in the cost of the entire construction. Permanent formwork as a new technology in construction first appeared in the USA, then migrated to Europe, after which it began to be used by builders in the CIS countries [1]. This development cycle means that in a variety of climatic conditions it has confirmed its high efficiency, and in recent years it has begun to enjoy popularity in the Republic of Uzbekistan [3, 4].

Permanent formwork is blocks or panels made of different materials that are mounted into a single monolithic formwork structure. This technology speeds up and simplifies construction by combining several processes into one technological cycle [2, 5]. The principle of permanent formwork consists in monolithic concreting

of walls in formwork, which, unlike prefabricated formwork, is not dismantled after the concrete has set, but becomes part of the structure.

The construction of a building using permanent formwork is reminiscent of monolithic construction, but the formwork here plays a slightly different role. In monolithic construction, formwork is used as an inventory, and in permanent formwork it acts as a material for the general structure [7, 8]. The idea of using permanent formwork is very simple: build a wall row by row, filling it with concrete and inserting reinforcing bars to increase spatial rigidity. The result is a strong frame structure - a reinforced concrete lattice, internal and external surfaces, which are reliably insulated. And if the task is to build a house in the shortest possible time according to a unique project, then construction using this technology will be the most correct solution [5, 6].

To date, designers have developed several types of permanent formwork, the installation technology of each of which is carried out according to certain rules: careful preparation of the future structure, correct installation on the foundation, as well as careful pouring of a special concrete mixture [9, 10]. This technology allows you to implement projects of any complexity. Both natural (wood in the form of chips) and artificial (expanded polystyrene) materials are used as starting materials for permanent formwork. Let's consider the most popular options for permanent formwork that the construction industry can offer us today.

Elements of permanent formwork are classified depending on the material of the walls, by shape - corner, intermediate, for walls with non-standard angles, as well as by wall thickness [12]. The classic type of permanent formwork is polystyrene foam blocks. Its essence is that it is assembled from hollow blocks of expanded polystyrene, which are connected to each other using groove fasteners, then the blocks are reinforced and filled with concrete [11, 13]. Despite their lightness, they are quite durable, are excellent insulators and at the same time do not interfere with the necessary air circulation; the process of constructing structural elements is quite simple. Such blocks are easy to process, so you can use their non-

standard elements, allowing you to erect a building according to a unique design, and even in winter [14, 15].

Based on the results of laboratory tests and practical experience of use, we can say that the sanitary safety of such formwork is confirmed by hygienic certificates, the owners of buildings built using this technology do not experience discomfort or health problems, and the fire safety of polystyrene foam blocks complies with current standards. They belong to the category of low-flammability and low-flammability materials (G1 and B1). But their level of smoke formation is quite high - D3. The only drawback of this type of formwork can be considered the possibility of one-time use, since blocks of polystyrene foam remain forever in the concrete wall of the building.

The use of fiberboard boards in permanent formwork is also one of the newest promising trends in construction. Fiberboard slabs are made from small wood shavings and caustic magnesite, the absence of which is most often replaced with Portland cement. This material is environmentally friendly, easy to process, which makes it possible to produce structures of any shape. The main advantages include biostability, fire safety, high vapor permeability and frost resistance. Internal and external wall finishing is carried out using standard technology. No less popular for permanent formwork are wood (chip-cement) boards.

They are produced by semi-dry pressing of wood waste with cement. This type of formwork is characterized by high sound and heat insulation properties, due to the presence in the material of a large number of air bubbles, which are evenly distributed between the wooden chips. Special chemical treatment of wood makes the material as resistant to high levels of humidity as possible, to the rapid process of rotting and burning, which allows the use of this type of formwork when constructing floors. The technology for manufacturing and installing permanent formwork is almost the same as using fiberboard boards.

Having considered all the advantages and disadvantages of permanent formwork, it should be admitted that this construction development is quite exciting

and promising. The construction of buildings using permanent formwork is, of course, the next step in the evolution of construction.

It should be noted that when using this technology, the principles of construction have not changed, and the stages of work have been reduced by almost half. The technology using permanent formwork is simple, but maximum precision and accuracy of the work is required.

As in the classical development of events, the construction of a building begins with the construction of the foundation. Even at the design stage, the calculation of the foundation structure is carried out taking into account two main conditions - the bearing capacity of the soil and the magnitude of the operating loads from the future building. Depending on this, the area of the foundation and the class of concrete are calculated.

A traditional strip concrete foundation is laid in formwork on sand and crushed stone beds laid in succession. Most often, pile foundations with a monolithic reinforced concrete grillage are installed. At the foundation construction stage, vertical outlet rods are laid in it to connect with the wall. Their length should be sufficient to install the first three rows of formwork.

In addition, inside each row, horizontal red reinforcing bars are laid to ensure longitudinal rigidity of the frame. It is also necessary to waterproof the first row of formwork. After completing the foundation, installation of permanent formwork for the construction of walls begins. The formwork slabs are fixed using release rods left in the foundation. These rods serve as the basis for the formation of new layers of reinforcing mesh. When installing the first row, the locations of future doorways and the junction of internal walls are carefully verified. Next, the reinforcing mesh and both walls of the permanent formwork are gradually built up. It is necessary to ensure the laying of channels for communication networks in advance.

The process of concreting walls is carried out traditionally using a concrete pump with a concrete mixture of class B15. The concrete mixture is laid in layers, the height of the tier is 1.2-1.6 m with compaction using a high-frequency deep

vibrator. After concreting, the walls are leveled for linearity and verticality. At the final stage of construction, the concrete is cared for and its curing process is monitored, as well as the installation of floors and roofs. After installing the roof, finishing work begins.

Permanent formwork allows you to use all classic materials for interior and exterior decoration: brick, plaster, siding, facing stone, wall plinth panels, tiles. Modern polymer adhesive mixtures allow you to attach everything to polystyrene foam.

Conclusions. So, if we analyze modern construction, then development using permanent formwork occupies one of the leading places in it in terms of size. It is economical, simple and reliable. It can be used for the construction of energy-saving and prefabricated buildings, individual and multi-storey residential buildings, high-rise public buildings, shops, swimming pools, garages, etc. This is a great opportunity to build a warm, high-quality, cozy house that any developer will be happy with.

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